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Inequality and inclusion in Swedish early childhood education and care: a policy analysis

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Abstract

At the intersection of education and policy, one of the most persistent problems is that of addressing inequalities through inclusive education. In line with efforts to address this problem, we present findings from a European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation project called *Educational Common Spaces: Passing through enclosures and reversing inequalities*. The project brought together a consortium of twelve universities from eight European countries to study the question of inequality and inclusion in a variety of educational settings across the continent. In the present article we report on findings we contributed to one of the project's constituent studies: an analysis of Swedish policy and steering documents focused on inequality and inclusion in Early Childhood Education and Care (ECEC). We draw on and extend recent policy analyses of inclusive education in Sweden to engage in an examination of how ideas about inequality and inclusion are actualized across levels (national and municipal) and time scales (established and ongoing discourses) in the context of the early years. Our analysis of Swedish ECEC policy documents reveals a dominant logic in which inequalities are addressed through an inclusive education that is compensatory in nature, positioning the child as a *re-producer-reproducer of culture, knowledge, and values*, now particularly those associated with the *acquisition of Swedish language*. In relation to previous policy analyses, what comes forward as a new phenomenon here is the third point – the focus on early acquisition of the national language. This represents an important shift in policies and in the concluding discussion of this article we draw up some possible critical and creative ways of addressing this shift.

Keywords Early childhood education and care, Educational commons, Inequality, Inclusive education, Critical policy analysis, Sweden

Introduction: addressing inequalities through inclusive education

Inequalities in early childhood education and care (ECEC) are a serious challenge for educational systems that seek to promote inclusion of all children. In Sweden, there has been an increase in differences among preschools in terms of quality, alongside a dearth of research addressing issues of equality and inclusion at the ECEC level (Swedish Research Council, 2015). This domain of inquiry was recently identified by the

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Swedish Research Council (2023) to be one of three priority research areas in educational research.

These Swedish trends reflect broader European patterns, where children and youth encounter multiple inequalities at individual, school, and structural levels. At the individual level, inequalities stem from socioeconomic status, migration background, home language, gender, and cultural capital. School-level factors include teacher practices that shape students' perceptions and motivations, as well as institutional characteristics such as geographic location and curriculum interpretation—factors that can advance exclusionary practices and segregation. Structural inequalities operate at the systemic level through mechanisms such as school choice, grade repetition, educational streaming, ability-based tracking, and neoliberal trends promoting human capital approaches. These intersecting inequalities manifest in childhood and educational poverty, migration-related trauma, health disparities linked to family income and social capital, disabilities, family circumstances, technology access, and gender discrimination.¹

One way of addressing inequalities on a policy level is to promote more inclusive education. However, the meanings attached to inclusion have changed over time in response to political, economic, and social developments. Examining how these shifts appear in policy texts is important for understanding how expectations for children, educators, and ECEC institutions are constructed. Sweden offers a particularly relevant context for examining how these shifts are articulated in ECEC policy.

Given Sweden's reputation as a progressive welfare state, one might expect a coherent policy approach to addressing inequalities through inclusive education. However, Swedish ECEC policy has undergone significant changes over the past several decades. These shifts reflect broader reforms in governance, accountability, and curricula. They have contributed to ongoing debates about the purpose of ECEC, the responsibilities placed on educators, and the ways in which inclusion is expected to be realized in practice. These developments provide important context for understanding how contemporary ECEC policy constructs inequality and inclusion.

The study presented in this article examines how inequality and inclusion are conceptualized at the policy level in the Swedish ECEC system. It was conducted within the Horizon 2020 project *Educational Common Spaces: Passing through enclosures and reversing inequalities* (hereafter SMOOTH project; Cappello et al., 2024), a multi-site, international project designed to address how inequalities could be reversed through more inclusive education. Partner teams across Europe explored whether values and practices associated with The Commons,² such as participation, sharing, and co-creation, might support more inclusive educational environments. As members of the

¹These findings emerge from systematic reviews conducted within the Horizon 2020 project *Educational Common Spaces: Passing through enclosures and reversing inequalities* (Cappello et al., 2024). The research presented in this article was conducted as part of the Swedish team's contribution to this project. For detailed documentation of the inequality factors across Europe, discussed in this paragraph, see SMOOTH (2024a & 2024b).

²The paradigm of The Commons can be understood as an alternative system of values and collective practices for organizing social life, one that supports democratic ideals, promotes equality, encourages creativity, and fosters sustainable relationships between people and their environments (Bauwens et al., 2019). Concepts associated with The Commons, including common-pool resources (Ostrom, 1990) and commons-based peer production (Benkler & Nissenbaum, 2006), refer to goods and resources that are collectively produced, shared, and governed. Communities that generate or manage such resources emphasize participatory forms of decision-making and value equality in their administration. At its core, the commons reflect practices of sharing and co-responsibility. Within the SMOOTH project, this paradigm served as a conceptual backdrop for exploring participatory and inclusive educational practices across a variety of formal and informal settings; in the present article, we draw on it only as contextual background rather than as an analytical framework.

Swedish team, we contributed to all components of this broader project. The present article reports on one part of that work: an analysis of national and municipal policy and steering documents examining how inequality and inclusion are framed in contemporary Swedish ECEC policy.

To situate the analysis, the next section outlines a historical background to key international and Swedish developments in research and policy related to addressing inequalities through inclusive education.

Background: international and Swedish developments in inclusive education

Researchers often cite the Salamanca Statement (UNESCO, 1994) as the starting point for an international movement of inclusive education in practice, research and policy (Nilholm, 2021). This movement signalled a resistance towards segregating aspects and systems of “special” education and embraced an idea of diversity as a fundamental feature of all educational practice. As several researchers have shown (Florian, 2008, 2019; Haug, 1998, 2017; Kiuppis, 2013; Magnússon, 2023), the Statement introduced both ethical commitments and practical dilemmas that continue to shape the field. These dilemmas include questions about who is to be included, into what kinds of settings, and through which practices. At the same time these dilemmas throw into relief different ways in which inclusive education is defined: 1) the placement of children and pupils in need of special support in “special” schools or in regular classrooms (mainstreaming), 2) education’s responsibility for and response to children and pupils in need of special support, 3) education’s responsibility for and response to *all* children and pupils, and 4) education as the creation of “communities” (Nilholm, 2021). Although research on inclusive education has addressed its effects, challenges, and philosophical underpinnings, the field continues to grapple with imprecise definitions, differing assumptions about the purposes of inclusion, and tensions between ideals and available resources.

Tensions that have persisted in the field are reflected in ambiguities within the Salamanca Statement itself. Among the various political ideas expressed in the statement, one finds education described as both a public and private good, with economic rationalities running in parallel to more ethical arguments (Magnússon, 2019, 2023). The Statement and the corresponding fields of research, practice, and policy that subsequently emerged, thus encompass a “multitude of interpretations of what inclusion can mean” (Magnússon, 2019, p. 687). This “amalgam of ideals” (Magnússon, 2019), has helped the notion of inclusion to expand, but it has also led to definitions that may conflict or lead policy and practice in counterproductive directions. These long-standing debates provide an important background for understanding contemporary policy framings of inequality and inclusion.

Sweden’s policy trajectory reflects many of these international developments while also reflecting unique features shaped by its history as a welfare state. Sweden is often associated with strong commitments to equality and participation. Its social-democratic tradition stresses the redistributive role of the state in creating conditions for the achievement of equal education for all children. It’s a model designed to support availability of and accessibility to equal educational opportunities in order to eliminate the economic obstacles to full participation.

To this end Sweden’s educational system provides all children and youth with subsidized early childhood education and care and after school programs. While primary

and secondary education is free of charge, preschool provision involves a sliding-scale fee based on household income, capped by a national maximum. No fee is required to attend either municipal or independent ‘free’ schools; however, both types of schools must follow the same curricula. Funding is provided by the national government, with municipalities having the discretion for distributing these funds based on locally defined needs and the number of students enrolled in the school.

In line with this, Sweden’s education system is formally grounded in democratic values and human rights. The Swedish Education Act (2010:800) specifies that education must be conducted in accordance with principles such as the equal value of all people, respect for individual freedom and integrity, and a commitment to equality and solidarity. It also states that all professionals working in education are required to promote human rights and actively work against all forms of degrading treatment.

Despite these clearly articulated values, Swedish education is shaped by a complex web of national legislation, regulations, curricula, and local documents, as well as by international agreements and legislation (Magnússon et al., 2019). These frameworks communicate political intentions and ideas about the purposes, priorities, and organization of education. Yet, as Magnússon et al. (2019) note, policy can still give rise to “organizational approaches that are not in line with ambitions to reduce segregating and excluding practices,” (p.75). At the classroom level, for example, these values can be difficult to attain and practice when the broader system and policy environment begins to act in contradictory ways (Magnússon et al., 2019).

Related to this, one clear challenge to inclusive education in Sweden is the growing influence of individualization and marketization of education over the past three decades (Biesta, 2010). Features associated with these logics, such as accountability, standardization, and free school choice, are now prominent across classroom- system- and policy levels (Bunar, 2011, 2022; Magnússon, 2023). Magnússon (2023), drawing on Göransson et al. (2011) and Isaksson and Lindqvist (2015), argues that these developments have contributed to a policy shift from equity toward efficiency. In this view, inclusion has largely disappeared as a political priority. It is seldom mentioned in recent government statements or policy documents, and organizational solutions that have segregating effects are becoming more common among both municipal and independent providers. These trends, Magnússon suggests, weaken the structural conditions needed to support inclusive education.

In ECEC research, this tendency was identified in the 1990s and early 2000s, when the now classic works of Gunilla Dahlberg, Peter Moss and Alan Pence (Dahlberg et al., 1999/2013; Dahlberg & Moss, 2005) threw into relief the contradictions and tensions associated with different discourses of quality and equality in ECEC. These works were foundational to Routledge’s *Contesting Early Childhood* series, which has become a leading forum for critical scholarship on ECEC. The scholarship in this series advances substantive critiques of how individualization and marketization undermine inclusive education and alternative theoretical and practical approaches to equity and inclusion. Two recent volumes exemplify this tradition, examining the commodification of ECEC while proposing approaches for critically and creatively de-commodify ECEC (Roberts-Holmes & Moss, 2021; Vandenbroeck et al., 2023).

Within the SMOOTH Project (see above), we, the Swedish research team, together with a group of preschool teachers, headteachers and artists, collaborated to explore

viable ways of contributing to this body of scholarship through both critique and the creation of more equal and inclusive education in the early years (Olsson et al., 2024). We (the researchers within this team) have backgrounds in continental philosophical, pedagogical and didactical theories. This position us close to the above-mentioned approach to inclusive education from a philosophical perspective (Magnússon, 2023), concerning the very conceptualizations of education, inequality and inclusion, as well as to the definition of inclusive education in relation to education's responsibility for and response to all children and pupils (Nilholm, 2021). However, the team is equally oriented towards the definition of inclusive education as the creation of communities

(Nilholm, 2021) given our engagement in long-term ethnographic fieldwork inspired by the paradigm of the Commons and innovative methodologies such as a pedagogy of listening, pedagogical documentation and project-work.

Our team engaged in all SMOOTH Project work-packages, including a long-term case study involving the teachers, headteachers, and artists in our team. Taken together, our participation in all the work packages positioned us to study inequalities and inclusion at the system, school and classroom levels, all deemed relevant for studying these phenomena (Nilholm, 2021). In the present article we examine the system-level. In what follows, we develop this system level analysis by exploring how inequality and inclusion are addressed in municipal and national policies in Swedish ECEC. We draw on and adapt a set of overarching questions that were posed in the SMOOTH Project to guide analysis of policy at this level:

- How do official policy discourses engage with education, inequality, and inclusion?
- Which subject positions do these interpretations create and allow for children?
- Which dominant beliefs and ideas about children's social, environmental, and political activity, and their entitlement to participate in public life, do the discourses include?

Conceptual and methodological approach: philosophically grounded policy analysis and the “what’s the problem represented to be?” method

Our conceptual and methodological approach follows perspectives in research that treat policy texts as negotiated artefacts shaped by broader policy logics. Following Ball's (1993) distinction between policy as text and discourse, where texts are open to interpretation yet shaped by established ways of describing and addressing issues, we read Swedish ECEC policy not only for what it states but for the assumptions and expectations that organize how these policies frame problems. Furthermore, drawing on Bacchi's (1999, 2009) insight that policies represent issues in particular ways, we examine how representations of inequality and inclusion become intelligible and authoritative within Swedish ECEC policy. Bacchi's (2009) argument is that policies do not just respond to problems but help shape what counts as a problem in the first place. From this view, analysing policy involves studying how issues are described, what assumptions underpin those descriptions, and what is left out or taken for granted. For our purposes, this means examining how Swedish ECEC policy describes inequality and inclusion, what these ways of describing make visible, and what kinds of expectations they place on educators, children, and institutions. Following this understanding of policy as both text and discourse, we analyze diverse policy texts that operate at different levels of the

education system and that each contribute to how problems are represented (e.g. laws, curricula, governmental investigations).

To deepen this approach, we specifically adopt Bacchi's 'What's the Problem Represented to be?' (WPR) method (Bacchi, 1999, 2009; Bacchi & Goodwin, 2016) and situate it with complementary insights from continental philosophers Henri Bergson (1859–1941) and Gilles Deleuze (1925–1995), psychotherapist Félix Guattari (1930–1992), and historian of ideas Michel Foucault (1926–1984). Both Bacchi's approach and these philosophical perspectives share a concern with how problems are constructed rather than given, how social and political institutions create categories of need and deficiency, and how subject-positions are created by knowledge-traditions informing problem formulations (Bergson, 1934/2007; Deleuze & Guattari, 1984; Foucault, 1977). As Bergson and Deleuze argue, how a problem is constructed gives sense and meaning both to the problem and its solution. It is these constructs that need to be studied for their limits and potentials. And as Foucault has shown throughout his body of work, what lies behind the construction of problems are complex entanglements of historical and contemporary scientific knowledge with the power relations that produce discursive regimes governing how we think, act and talk about ourselves as subjects.

Taken together, these perspectives help clarify how some ways of describing educational issues come to shape what is expected in practice. Even though policy texts are negotiated documents, they still reveal the ideas and priorities that guide educational systems, including how different actors and responsibilities with these systems are imagined. For our study, this meant examining how Swedish ECEC constructs and circulates meanings of inequality and inclusion.

The construction of concepts like inclusion and inequality in policy is a challenge to analyse both because they are open to interpretation and because policy is continually contested and interpreted by those initiating it, those implementing it, and external actors. This is true in the Swedish context. As noted in Sect. "[Background: international and Swedish developments in inclusive education](#)", Swedish education policy reflects competing political intentions, with inclusion rarely foregrounded as a policy priority and often left undefined in official documents, while at the same time being shaped by trends toward marketization and efficiency (Magnússon, 2023; Magnússon et al., 2019). In this context of shifting priorities, analyzing how problems are constructed becomes especially important.

A strength of the WPR approach for our purposes is its applicability across multiple policy levels. While Bacchi does not prescribe a fixed hierarchy of policy levels, the WPR framework is designed for examining how problem representations circulate through and are shaped by different sites of policy production (e.g. from legal texts at the national level, to curricular ones that "translate" legal principles through pedagogical guidelines, to local implementation plans that specify how policies are to be enacted in particular institutional contexts). This allows for assessing how problem representations are contested or reinforced as they move through levels of the system. In the Swedish ECEC context, this multi-level approach is especially relevant given the relatively decentralized nature of educational governance, where national legislation establishes broad frameworks that are then interpreted and implemented by municipalities and individual preschools.

Bacchi (2009) describes WPR as having a broad field of application across various types of policy texts, from specific pieces of legislation to general government documents to institutional guidelines. In line with this approach, our analysis examines problem representations at three interconnected levels: (1) the national level, including legislation (the Swedish Education Act, the Discrimination Act) and governmental investigations; (2) the policy guidance level, including the national preschool; and (3) the municipal level, comprising local action plans and guidelines that specify how national policies are to be implemented in particular contexts.

By analyzing documents across these levels, we trace how problem representations of inequality and inclusion are articulated and reproduced from broad legislative statements through to concrete implementation guidelines. This approach allows us to identify not only what problems are represented at each level, but also how these representations are reinforced or contested across the policy system. Drawing on Bacchi's (2009) WPR approach—which asks: What is the problem represented to be? What presuppositions underlie this representation? What is left unproblematic? How has this representation emerged, and what effects does it produce?—in combination with Ball's policy theory and philosophical perspectives, we operationalized the overarching research questions introduced in Sect. "[Background: international and Swedish developments in inclusive education](#)" by formulating specific analytic questions to direct our examination of Swedish ECEC policy documents.

- Research question: How do official policy discourses engage with inequality and inclusive education? Analytic question: *How is the problem of inequality and inclusive education defined in different documents at different levels in the policy-system?*
- Research question: Which subject positions do these interpretations create and allow for children? Analytic question: *Which scientific underpinnings are activated in written descriptions of children and what kind of subject is portrayed?*
- Research question: Which dominant beliefs and ideas about children's social, environmental and political activity, and their entitlement to participate in public life, do the discourses include? Analytic question: *How do definitions of inequality and inclusive education as well as positions attributed to children play out in dominant beliefs and ideas about their participation in public life?*

In line with the WPR method, the selection of documents to analyze was guided by the need to capture how concepts of inequality and inclusion are framed and operationalized across different levels of governance (national and municipal) and timescales (established and ongoing discourses on education, equality and inclusion) in Swedish ECEC policy. We therefore selected policy documents that included national laws, governmental investigations, the national preschool curriculum and a municipal action plan and guidelines:

The Swedish Education Act (2010:800)

The Discrimination Act (2008:567)

Governmental Investigation on equality and social inclusion in primary and secondary school *A more equal school – Decreased segregation and increased distribution of resources* (SOU 2020:28)

Governmental Investigation recommending compulsory preschool for certain children *More children in preschool – For better language acquisition in Swedish* (SOU 2020:67)

The Swedish preschool curriculum (National Agency of Education, 2018)

A municipal-level action plan for preschool education (Preschool Board's Action Plan, 2021)

The Swedish Education Act (2010:800) and The Discrimination Act (2008:567) were included as they provide the overarching legal foundation for educational equality and non-discrimination in Sweden, setting the broad parameters for inclusion. The Governmental Investigation Reports (SOU 2020:28 and SOU 2020:67) were selected because they offer policy recommendations and perspectives on contemporary debates related to social inclusion and language acquisition in preschool, highlighting ongoing governmental efforts to address inequalities. The Swedish Preschool Curriculum (National Agency of Education, 2018) was included to examine how these legal principles are translated into pedagogical guidelines and expectations within ECEC settings. Finally, the municipal action plan (Preschool Board's Action Plan, 2021) was included to capture how national policies and curriculum are interpreted and enacted at the local implementation level.

The analysis of the documents was conducted collaboratively by the three authors, using an iterative, interpretive approach. These analyses were guided by the analytic questions derived from our overarching research questions, which were informed and structured by the policy and philosophical frameworks described above. We engaged in multiple rounds of collaborative readings and reflexive discussions, focused on underlying assumptions, and subject positions constructed through the language of the selected documents. This iterative process allowed us to systematically apply the analytic questions to the different policy texts, allowing for examination of how inclusion and inequality are addressed across various levels of governance while ensuring depth and consistency in interpretation.

Results and discussion

Herein we present the findings from our analysis of the policy documents, focusing on how the problem of inequality and inclusion is framed and operationalized in Swedish ECEC.³ The analysis is structured around the three core analytic questions which, as outlined in Sect. "[Conceptual and methodological approach: philosophically grounded policy analysis and the “what’s the problem represented to be?” method](#)", were derived from and structured by Bacchi's (2009) WPR approach, each enacting a distinct dimension of that framework. Sect. "[How is the problem of inequality and inclusive education defined in different documents at different levels in the policy-system?](#)" examines what the problem of inequality, inclusion, and education is represented to be in the policy documents and what presuppositions underlie that representation. It identifies a compensatory logic that frames inequality as a problem to be addressed at the classroom-level rather than as a structural concern. Sect. "[Which scientific underpinnings are activated in written descriptions of children and what kind of subject is portrayed?](#)" explores how children

³All excerpts from the analysed documents have been translated by the authors to best convey the original meaning in Swedish.

are positioned as subjects in these policies, examining what subject-positions these representations produce and which scientific knowledge-traditions make them possible, identifying dominant perspectives and scientific underpinnings in which children are framed as passive recipients and re-producers of culture, knowledge, and values, rather than as active co-constructors. Sect. "[How do definitions of inequality and inclusive education as well as positions attributed to children play out in dominant beliefs and ideas about their participation in public life?](#)" investigates how these definitions of inequality and inclusion together with the subject-positions attributed to children play out in dominant ideas of the participation in public life as dependent upon their early acquisition of the Swedish language, attending to what is left unproblematic in these representations and what effects they produce.

How is the problem of inequality and inclusive education defined in different documents at different levels in the policy-system?

Our analyses of the national-level documents revealed that the task and mission of education in relation to inequality and inclusion are described in similar if not identical terms. These concern the idea that the purpose of education is for children to acquire a predetermined set of cultural knowledge and values, and that education therefore has a *compensatory* task. We first draw on the Education Act (2010:800) to illustrate this general description:

Excerpt 1

Within the school system the goal of education is for children and students to acquire and develop knowledge and values. It should promote the development and learning of all children and students as well as a lifelong desire to learn. The education must also convey and anchor respect for human rights and the fundamental democratic values on which Swedish society rests.

Excerpt 2

Education must take into account the different needs of children and students. Children and students should be given support and stimulation so that they develop as much as possible. One aim should be to compensate for differences in the children's and students' ability to assimilate the education.

(Chapter 1, § 4)

Excerpts 1 and 2 highlight an aspect of the discourse on education, inequality and inclusion, that is articulated not only at the national level and in the Education Act (2010:800), but in all the documents analysed: education is to be organized around the goal of children and youth acquiring a predetermined set of cultural knowledge and values. Because children grow up in different social and cultural contexts, they are seen as having unequal access to these predefined sets of knowledge and values. As a result, education is framed as a *compensatory* mechanism, tasked with bridging these perceived gaps to promote inclusion and reduce inequalities.

Another example of how this compensatory task is articulated can be seen at the national level in the Governmental Investigation *More children in preschool – For better language acquisition in Swedish* (SOU 2020:67). The investigation proposes the *compensatory* move of making preschool compulsory:

Excerpt 3

A compulsory preschool means that preschool can compensate for differences in children's upbringing conditions and contribute to more equal pre-requisites before school-start. (SOU 2020:67, p. 20)

Even though making preschool compulsory would be an action taken at the structural level, the very definition of education, inequality and inclusion is made on a classroom-level: it is here that the problem is identified, and it is here that the solution is to be found. This also applies in the local municipal policy-document that we have analysed, a “plan of action” document published by a preschool board which makes decisions concerning early childhood centres in a Swedish municipality (Preschool Board's Action Plan, 2021). The document lays out the goals and priorities for the early childhood centres in the municipality during 2021. Here, inequality and inclusion are defined as a problem in a way that is nearly identical to how it is addressed in the Education Act (2010:800): the problem is to be solved through compensating, at a classroom level, for each child's individual background, so that each child can develop “as much as possible”:

Excerpt 4

The aim of equality in preschool is to ensure that every child receives an education that is designed and adapted so that every child, regardless of circumstances and background, develops as much as possible.

(Preschool Board's Action Plan, 2021, p.5)

In all the documents the problem of education, inequality and inclusion is defined as a question of compensation at the classroom-level, and not as a structural issue concerning wider societal problems such as housing segregation or the distribution of economic resources to education. This definition of the problem is further highlighted by the focus on the individual child that runs through all documents analysed.

In line with previous research (Biesta, 2010; Bunar, 2011, 2022; Dahlberg et al., 1999/2013, Dahlberg & Moss, 2005; Göransson et al., 2011; Isaksson & Lindqvist, 2015; Magnússon, 2023; Roberts-Holmes & Moss, 2021; Vandebroek et al., 2023), in nearly all documents when inequality and inclusion are invoked they are related to descriptions of individual children's different needs. In nearly all documents, education, inequalities and inclusion are framed, despite the invocation of universalist values, as an individual concern rather than a collective and democratic right (Biesta, 2006). It is the individual child and pupil that shall learn and develop, become equal and be included. However, the discourse on the individual child, and particularly, differences between individual children, is somewhat confused: at the same time as individual differences are highlighted, the compensatory function seems to aim at a certain “levelling out” of these differences.

Conceptions of difference articulated in all the analysed documents are made with strong correspondence to the above-mentioned compensatory function of education where culture, knowledge, and values are transmitted to children. Arguments addressing constructed categories of differences are explicitly expressed in the Discrimination Act (2008:567), where equal rights and educational opportunities are described as needing to be promoted regardless of gender, transgender identity or expression, ethnicity, religion or other belief, disability, sexual orientation or age. Thus, on the one hand, there is a perception that these categories are important to acknowledge and accommodate, but, on the other hand, there is a constant appeal to the role of education in “levelling out” of individual and inherent differences that may threaten equality and inclusion. The

contradictions in this discourse are evident, for example, in the preschool curriculum (National Agency of Education, 2018) where, on the one hand, differences, and the value of diversity are considered important for children and adults alike, but on the other, they are implicitly framed as a threat through the insistence upon transferring a given cultural heritage:

Excerpt 5

Education should be characterised by openness and respect for differences in people's perceptions and ways of life.

(National Agency of Education, 2018, p.5)

Excerpt 6

The preschool's task includes transferring and developing a cultural heritage – values, traditions and history, language and knowledge – from one generation to the next.

(National Agency of Education, 2018, p.9)

With few exceptions (e.g. the framing of multilingualism as positive in one sentence in the Preschool Board's Action Plan) all documents acknowledge differences between children in ways that are muted and under-valued. Through such framing of the problem, it is as if each child/pupil has a predetermined level of potential abilities and competencies that the school-system should engage, but only insofar as each individual is capable of reaching a prescribed measure of culture, knowledge, and values (i.e. that each child develop "as much as possible" in relation to these givens). Another example of this is found in *Excerpt 4* (Preschool Board's Action Plan, 2021, p.5) where the phrase "develop as much as possible" is used in a manner similar to how it is deployed in The Education Act (2010:800) and the curriculum (The National Agency of Education, 2018).

What is at stake in these discourses on difference is the fundamental educational and ethical question about the relation between the individual and society. On a deeper level, this question may be defined as concerning the relation between particularity and universality (Deleuze, 1994), and in education this plays out in the relation between the unique/particular individual, or local context, and the common/universal features of the group, or larger global, contexts (Popkewitz, 1998). In educational practice, this often implies the challenging task of creating an equilibrium between individual children and common educational practices, processes and products (Olsson et al., 2016) while paying careful attention to the transformative aspects of both individuals and education.

At no point in the analysed documents, however, do we see a more nuanced reasoning concerning this relation. In fact, these policies neglect current research on inclusive education (Florian, 2008, 2019; Haug, 1998, 2017; Kiuppis, 2013; Magnússon et al., 2019; Nilholm, 2021; Nilholm & Göransson, 2017),⁴ especially research on important questions concerning *who* is to be included by *whom* and into *what*, as well as research on the risk of stigmatization that inevitably arises when individuals are defined in terms of one or another category and "need".

Moreover, the emphasis on individualization is, as previous research has shown, reinforced by an economic logic that permeates the discourse on education, inequality, and inclusion across all analyzed documents (Biesta, 2010; Bunar, 2011, 2022; Dahlberg et al., 1999/2013, Dahlberg & Moss, 2005; Göransson et al., 2011; Isaksson & Lindqvist,

⁴For an updated overview of current research in the field of inclusive education, see Magnússon 2023.

2015; Magnússon, 2023; Roberts-Holmes & Moss, 2021; Vandenbroeck et al., 2023). This is expressed both in the allocation of economic resources and in the broader economic rationalization of education, including its marketization and commodification.

In all the documents analysed, the reversal of inequality and promotion of inclusion are explicitly invoked as a right to everyone's access to education independent of social and economic conditions. Regardless of whether one lives in the country or in the city, in a high- or low-income area, one must have equal access to education. This is exemplified in the national curriculum for preschool, which itself invokes the Education act:

Excerpt 7

The Education Act stipulates that education should be of equivalent value regardless of where in the country it is provided. It should take into account the different conditions and needs of children and be adapted to all children in the preschool. This means that education cannot be structured in the same way everywhere and that the resources of the preschool should not be distributed equally.
(National Agency of Education, 2018,p.7)

The curriculum goes on to explain the need to differentiate the allocation and arrangement of resources based on the identification and description of differences in the need for these resources by different schools:

Excerpt 8

The preschool should pay particular attention to children who need more guidance and stimulation or special support for various reasons. All children should receive an education that is designed and adapted so that they develop as far as possible. Children who need more support and stimulation, either temporarily or permanently, should be provided with this, structured according to their own needs and conditions.
(*ibid*)

However, this resource-distribution seems not function in practice. The Governmental Investigation *More children in preschool – For better language acquisition in Swedish* reports that less than half of Swedish providers of ECEC adopt a socioeconomic resource-distribution approach based on a logic of equity for preschools based on their differing conditions (SOU 2020:67, p.214–215). The same investigation shows that differences in terms of equal access to education have instead increased with the privatization of the Swedish school system (SOU 2020:46, p.17).

Associated with definitions of inequality and inclusive education in the analysed documents, is the idea that all children have the right to *equal quality* of education (National Agency of Education, 2018, p.7). However, the definition of quality is largely absent in the analysed documents, and yet systematic work with quality-improvement is mentioned as key to obtaining more equitable education. Such work is highlighted at the local, municipal level in the “plan of action” document published by the preschool board:

Excerpt 9

The preschools must maintain a high level of pedagogical quality and provide security and care in an environment that is stimulating for the children. The administration can state that the municipality's preschools at an overall level show good results, but that there are differences between and within preschools. In order to

increase equality in preschool, the administration prioritizes systematic quality work based on the national goals in the curriculum.
(Preschool Board's Action Plan, 2021, p.5)

This excerpt highlights how early childhood centers in the municipality are governed by both individualized and economic logics, reinforcing the “paradox of decentralization” that previous research has identified and where control is exercised through a quality discourse and measured by standardized protocols and accountability procedures (Dahlberg et al., 1999; Taubman, 2009). This form of governmentality (Foucault, 1977) can also be seen in the Governmental Investigation on economic equality (SOU 2020:28). The investigation reports an increase in the privatization of education, which is evident in the municipality, as it describes the explicit goal to privatize at least 50% of the early childhood centres in its action plan from 2020. This ambition is still prevalent for 2021, and the plan of action mentions this as one of the priorities for 2021:

Excerpt 10

Furthermore, in order to meet the need for increased freedom of choice, the municipality needs to make it easier for principals of independent preschools to start and run educational activities in the community. (Preschool Board's Action Plan , 2021, p. 5)

In summary, our analyses of the policy documents reveal the failure to adequately consider those risks that previous policy-analyses have identified concerning individualization, marketization and “free school choice” as factors further driving inequalities and counter-acting inclusion (Biesta, 2010; Bunar, 2011, 2022; Dahlberg & Moss, 2005; Göransson et al., 2011; Isaksson & Lindqvist, 2015; Magnússon, 2023; Vandenbroeck et al., 2023). While previous research has identified both the logics of individualization and an economic rationality in education (Isaksson & Lindqvist, 2015; Magnússon, 2023; Roberts-Holmes & Moss, 2021), our analyses reveal that these framings lead to a hegemonic idea of compensation at a classroom level as the prioritized means to address inequality and inclusion in ECEC. Moreover, these definitions of inequality and inclusion are consistently reproduced from national legislation through to municipal implementation, with municipalities adopting rather than adapting national problem representations. This uniformity across a decentralized system, where one might expect local variation, suggests that the policy discourse offers limited space for alternative framings within the analysed documents. Importantly, defining inequality and inclusive education primarily in compensatory terms also has consequences for how children are positioned as subjects in these texts. It is to this, and to the underlying scientific underpinnings of such positions, that we now turn.

Which scientific underpinnings are activated in written descriptions of children and what kind of subject is portrayed?

Across the documents analysed, the policy language implicitly draws on an information processing/transmission metaphor in which culture, knowledge, and values are treated as predetermined and transferable content, assumed to be amenable to standard interpretation (Wertsch, 1991). When children's active engagement in education is discussed, it is done by appealing to children's interests, opinions, and possibilities for making choices regarding questions that concern them, but not in terms of what contributions

they can make. This suggests certain limitations in relation to the position of children: The implied expectation is that they do not influence or transform culture, values and knowledge, but rather inherit already defined culture, values and knowledge. It is also clear that children are positioned as active, creative, competent and responsible citizens only once they have acquired these. That is, they are *yet to become* such citizens. An example of this is to be found in the Education Act (2010:800):

Excerpt 11

The education also aims to, in collaboration with the home, promote children's and students' all-round personal development into active, creative, competent and responsible individuals and citizens. (Chapter 1, § 4)

Inequality and inclusion in Swedish education are most often mentioned in the analysed documents in relation to children being described as “newly arrived to Sweden”, “deficient in the Swedish language”, and/or having a “weak socio-economic background” (SOU 2020:67:13). While we critique the ways in which policies frame differences as deficiencies, we recognize that these differences are real and must be addressed in educational practice, research and policy. Our critique focuses on how these needs are addressed in policy, often leading to deficit-based approaches that reduce children to subjects in need of intervention rather than active participants in their own education.

There is no discussion in the analysed documents on the potentially reductive image that a “child in need” produces. As noted by Deleuze and Guattari (1984) and Foucault (1977), needs are culturally and socially situated, even produced, just as the idea of “need” often equals a “lack” of something. Children are thus positioned in this formulation as “lacking”, rather than as active contributors to society (Olsson, 2009).

More specifically, our analyses revealed five contrasting and interrelated ways in which children were positioned as subjects:

1. tabula rasa
2. re-producer of culture, knowledge, and values
3. co-producer of culture, knowledge, and values
4. human capital
5. linguistic and logocentric beings

Predominant throughout all the documents was a framing that integrated positionings of children as tabula rasa (a blank slate upon which to inscribe culture, knowledge, and values), reproducers of culture, knowledge, and values (children inherit and repeat, but do not transform, given culture, knowledge, and values), human capital (early intervention and “investment” is economically beneficial for society) and linguistic-logocentric beings (children’s early acquisition of linguistic competencies are in focus). In most of the documents, there was language that divided children into those with or without desired competencies, but particularly, in terms of Swedish language fluency. This was most striking in our analyses of the Governmental Investigation *More children in pre-school – For better language acquisition in Swedish* (SOU 2020:67). As stated above, this investigation defined certain children as “newly arrived” to Sweden, as having a “language deficiency”, or a “weak socio-economic background”, and argued that such children should be automatically enrolled in early childhood services by the age of 3. The *dividing practices* (Foucault, 1977; Palla, 2021) that this proposal enforces are thrown

into relief by the rationale the government investigation articulates for making such a proposal. This is done in response to the argument that the discriminatory effects of such a proposal could be mitigated by requiring the enrolment of *all* children at the age of 3 years in preschool. Tellingly, this alternative is not investigated in the report (e.g. no financial calculations are included for this option), even though both the directive and the title of the text of the investigation indicate that this should be done. The motive for not doing this is that the actions taken need to be directed at those who are deemed in need of them:

Excerpt 12

As the Investigation considers that it is important that the actions taken focus on the children that really are in need of preschool for their development of the Swedish language, we have limited direct enrolment to children that can be assessed as having such needs.

(SOU 2020:67 p.268)

Turning to the question of the underpinning scientific paradigms, our analyses revealed that these varied in relation to the noted subject positions. In the case of the image of the child/youth as “tabula rasa” and “re-producers of culture, knowledge, and values” the underlying paradigm, as already shown by previous research, is often that of the scientific discipline of psychology, and most often developmental psychology (Dahlberg & Lenz-Taguchi, 1994, Dahlberg et al., 1999/2013). From this perspective the child is constructed as developing according to predetermined stages and proceeding along a “normal curve” (Dahlberg et al., 1999/2013). In the case of the child as human capital, the underlying paradigm, as also shown by previous research, often springs from both the economic and the political sciences (Moss, 2014; Roberts-Holmes & Moss, 2021; Vandebroek et al., 2023). As for the image of the child/youth as linguistic and logocentric beings, linguistic sciences, paired with the economic and political sciences seems to be at stake. It is also common, although not so much in the documents we have analysed here, that the linguistic sciences are combined with the neurosciences in the image of the logo-centric child (Vandebroek et al., 2017). Even though such foundations appeared only once in *More children in preschool – For better language acquisition in Swedish* (SOU 2020:67), we expect this scientific foundation of the image of the child to rapidly increase over the coming years (Vandebroek et al., 2017). It is noteworthy that it is only one of these images that originates from the educational and pedagogical sciences, namely the image of the child/youth as co-producer of culture, values, and knowledge (Dahlberg et al., 1999/2013). This also confirms our finding educational practices, policies and legislations are increasingly disconnected from the pedagogical knowledge-traditions that could support teachers and policymakers alike.

Of all the documents analyzed, only the Governmental Investigation (SOU 2020:67) includes explicit references to research. However, although it references relevant research across a range of fields, the investigation does not directly draw on research in the field of ECEC itself. In fact, much of the established national and international early childhood research contradicts the investigation’s premises, which are framed in terms of “school preparation” and “increased knowledge results”:

Excerpt 13

Children who have attended preschool have better cognitive and linguistic skills and achieve higher knowledge scores at school than children who have not participated in the preschool's activities.

(ibid, p.15)

A compulsory preschool can thus contribute in the long term to higher and more equal knowledge results in primary schools.

(ibid, p.20)

There is extensive national and international research critiquing the tendency to treat “early interventions” directed at individual groups of children as a panacea for current and future societal (predominantly economic) problems (Roberts-Holmes & Moss, 2021; Vandenbroeck et al., 2023). There is also a growing corpus of research showing that children’s creativity and cognitive flexibility are best supported by ensuring that ECEC activities afford collaborative and self-directed forms of social affiliation, play, and exploration (Gopnik, 2020; Gopnik et al., 2017; Lucas et al., 2014). This in contrast to ECEC approaches that prioritize school-based forms such as direct instruction, which in early childhood can decrease the chances that children will discover new information and develop original solutions to problems (Bonawitz et al., 2011; Buchsbaum et al., 2011). At the same time, there is work noting that the rush toward readiness for school in early childhood obscures the specificity of preschool as a protected and free space for children in the early years to engage in the kinds of playful and aesthetic exploration that are fundamental to the development of language and meaning making (Nilsson et al., 2018; Olsson et al., 2016).

To sum up: The strongest subject-position assigned to children in these policies is that of the child as a re-producer of culture, knowledge, and values, and now with a particular focus on the need for the child to reproduce these in relation to the Swedish language. This image of the child is primarily shaped by scientific disciplines outside the educational and pedagogical sciences. These are disciplines that tend to emphasize deficit-based images of the child and contribute to the “schoolification” of early childhood education and care. Meanwhile, perspectives from the pedagogical science, which could support an alternative view of children as *co-producers* of culture, knowledge, and values, including the Swedish language, are notably absent. In relation to scholarship that examines how neoliberal reforms privilege economic and psychological paradigms over pedagogical ones (Dahlberg et al., 1999; Moss, 2014; Roberts-Holmes & Moss, 2021), our analysis shows how this shift operates within Swedish ECEC now operates at all levels: the co-producer position is absent at all policy levels, while deficit-based positions rooted in psychology, economics, and linguistics are reproduced from national legislation to municipal implementation. This disciplinary consolidation reinforces the restricted policy space identified in Sect. ["How is the problem of inequality and inclusive education defined in different documents at different levels in the policy-system?"](#).

How do definitions of inequality and inclusive education as well as positions attributed to children play out in dominant beliefs and ideas about their participation in public life?

In terms of how the documents address children’s participation in public life, much of the analysis is driven by the answers to the first two research questions described above. Having established that problem representations of inequality and inclusion are reproduced across policy levels (Sect. ["How is the problem of inequality and inclusive](#)

education defined in different documents at different levels in the policy-system?") and that this uniformity is reinforced by the dominance of non-educational disciplinary paradigms (Sect. "Which scientific underpinnings are activated in written descriptions of children and what kind of subject is portrayed?"), we now consider how these patterns manifest in policy discourse on children's participation in public life. Across the analysed documents, inequality and inclusive education are defined in relation to a compensatory function of education, where the child is positioned as inheriting and reproducing given culture, knowledge, and values, particularly those associated with the Swedish language. As a result, the possibilities articulated for children's social and political participation in public life remain weak and constrained. As these definitions of inequality and inclusive education are rooted in individualistic and economic discourses that frame children as subjects of early intervention, the possibilities for participation in public life articulated in the documents are reduced to little more than having an opinion and making a choice. Moreover, when problems are poorly formulated, as when inequalities and inclusion are reduced to questions of individual and "vulnerable" children's and families' language-acquisition, rather than being related to systematic failures such as housing segregation and declining educational material environments—there is, as previous research has shown, a risk of further stigmatization of children and geographic areas labelled in this way (Bunar, 2011). Such definitions of children's participation in public life threaten to undermine both children's desires and possibilities to be fully part of society and public life.

This last point is perhaps the most important one. The compensatory function of education and the subject-position of children as reproducers of culture, knowledge, and values evoked in the analyzed documents appear to be grounded in dominant beliefs about children's active participation in public life as being solely and fundamentally dependent on their acquisition of Swedish language – not on the linguistic and extra-linguistic conditions offered to them for being able to participate at all. As stated above, our analysis reveals that education, equality, and inclusion are now, more than ever before (compare with Magnússon et al., 2019), strongly connected in policy and steering documents to children's early acquisition of the Swedish language. In the recent public debate in Sweden on immigration, a distinct rhetoric has emerged emphasizing acquisition of a national language as important for equality and inclusion in education. Traces of this debate are evident in the Governmental Investigation (SOU 2020:67) as well as the Swedish curriculum for preschool (National Agency of Education, 2018). For example, the curriculum's section on *Communication and Creation* begins by explicitly linking language acquisition to identity, and in the next breath emphasizing the importance of Swedish language acquisition:

Excerpt 14

Language, learning and the development of identity are closely linked. The preschool should therefore place great emphasis on stimulating children's language development in Swedish, by encouraging and taking into consideration their curiosity and interest in communicating in different ways.

(National Agency of Education, 2018, p.9)

The section goes on to emphasize the importance of communication in general, and arguably linking it to the rhetoric of the compensatory mission of education by orienting to notions of a common base of knowledge:

Excerpt 15

This will lay the foundation for children in due course to acquire the knowledge that everyone in society needs. The ability to communicate, seek new knowledge and collaborate is necessary in a society characterized by a high flow of information and continuous change.

(ibid)

The importance of policies that create conditions for children to acquire the language of the society in which they live is not in question, but this focus does come at a price, particularly for the youngest children. Young children's development and deployment of language, relative to adults, is more multimodal and needs to be addressed as such.

In summary, our analysis reveals that children's participation in public life is restricted by the definition of inequality and inclusive education as depending upon a compensatory function at a classroom level where the child is supposed to "inherit" given culture, knowledge, and values without reference to structural factors or pedagogical science. Further, and most importantly our analysis reveals a novelty in policies in relation to previous policy-analyses. While Magnússon et al. (2019) noted the relative absence of explicit inclusion discourse in Swedish education policy, we find that inequality and inclusive education are now explicitly foregrounded; however, they are reframed narrowly through the lens of Swedish language acquisition. Children's participation in public life is now described as heavily dependent on their early acquisition of the national language, representing an intensification and narrowing of inclusion discourse that reflects recent immigration debates in Sweden (Milani et al., 2021). This shift is significant because it simultaneously highlights and constrains a discourse of inclusion: inclusion is no longer absent from policy, but it has been redefined in linguistic terms that may reinforce rather than challenge exclusionary practices.

Conclusion: Expanding the Framework for Addressing Inequality through Inclusive Education in ECEC

Our analysis of Swedish ECEC policy documents reveals a dominant logic in which inequalities are addressed through inclusive education that is supposed to be: *compensatory*, and where the child is attributed a subject-position as a *re-producer of culture, knowledge, and values*, now particularly those associated with the *acquisition of Swedish language*. As noted earlier, previous policy analyses have identified an individualistic and economic logic in Swedish education policy, noting that policies limit inclusive options (Magnússon et al., 2019), define inclusion ambiguously (Göransson et al., 2011), and operate within deficit-based special needs discourses (Nilholm, 2021). Our analysis extends this work in three important ways. First, responding to Nilholm's (2021) call for system-level analyses, we traced problem representations of inequality and inclusion across national legislation, curriculum guidance, and municipal implementation. This revealed how such representations are reproduced across all levels, challenging both theoretical expectations of local adaptation and revealing the policy system's closure to internal contestation. Second, our analysis reveals a disciplinary shift in which

educational policies are now predominantly shaped by psychology, economics, and linguistic sciences rather than educational and pedagogical knowledge traditions, contributing to the “schoolification” of ECEC (Broström, 2017; Moss, 2013). Third, extending Magnússon et al.’s (2019) and Göransson et al.’s (2011) findings that inclusion was largely absent or unclear in Swedish policy, we identify a significant shift: inclusion and equality are now explicitly foregrounded but narrowly reframed through Swedish language acquisition. This represents both an intensification and a narrowing, illustrating what Nilholm (2021) warned against: inclusion defined within traditional special needs discourse rather than as a transformative educational project encompassing all children. This shift is worth emphasizing. Where previous research identified the absence of inclusion in Swedish ECEC policy, we find it has arrived, but in a form that may be more constraining than its absence, because it forecloses alternative framings under the appearance of progress.

These findings speak to issues that extend beyond the Swedish context. At the Nordic level, recent comparative research analyzing ECE policy in both Sweden and Denmark has independently identified similar dynamics, where the intersection of language policy, mandatory enrolment, and nationalist political trends has produced a narrowing of the inclusion discourse in both national contexts (Millei et al., 2025). More broadly, Millei and colleagues argue that these dynamics reflect a wider transformation in which welfare state universalism is being reframed around national belonging and majority language competence, a shift they identify as a form of nationalism that is not limited to the Nordic context but visible wherever increased migration is perceived as a threat to national cohesion. The mechanisms our analysis identifies are therefore likely to be recognizable to researchers and policymakers working in any context where migration, diversity, and ECEC governance intersect.

With these broader stakes in mind, we draw on our overarching research questions to structure a synthesis of the risks and potentials our findings reveal for addressing inequalities and promoting inclusive early childhood education, both in Sweden and in comparable contexts elsewhere.

How do official national policy discourses engage with education, inequality and inclusion? Our analysis showed that Swedish ECEC policy frames education as a compensatory mechanism, aimed at transmitting predefined culture, knowledge, and values. On the one hand, this reflects Sweden’s social-democratic tradition, where the state plays a redistributive role in fostering equality and inclusion. On the other hand, this *compensatory* view can obscure the *complementary*, transformative potential of education, and reduce children to recipients of intervention rather than active contributors to their learning.

Countering this risk requires policies that advance a more nuanced conception of the classical pedagogical mission of education: to create time and space for the new generations’ simultaneous study *and* transformation of culture, knowledge, and values. At the same time, a shift in policy discourse is needed that balances redistribution with children’s right to participation and transformation. As we show in our analysis, the compensatory function in the policies is also tightly connected to a focus on the individual and the “levelling out” of differences, but the arguments are weakened by their failure to engage with the foundational question of the relation between particularity and universality.

We pause here to note that while it is crucial to recognize individual needs, particularly for marginalized groups, we argue that a purely compensatory approach risks reducing children to subjects of intervention. In addition to targeted support, educational policies must also consider children's collective and democratic right to meaningful participation in education. This involves acknowledging what all children have in common: the need for a learning environment that respects their dignity, fosters their potential, and supports their transformation into active contributors to society. In line with this, we argue that educational practices should sometimes question preconceived notions about children's abilities and backgrounds, allowing space for their transformative potential to unfold.

Our findings align with Magnússon et al.'s (2019) observation that "as long as educational difficulties are viewed as results of individual shortcomings, marginalization and exclusion of pupils will prevail within the education system," (p.70). The compensatory logic we describe operates through this individualization. However, our analysis reveals a particular dimension: the uniformity with which compensatory, individualized framings are reproduced across levels of governance suggests that this individualization operates not just as a policy choice at any single level, but as a systemic logic that the decentralized structure fails to disrupt. This provides the kind of context-specific, empirically grounded analysis that Nilholm (2021) argues is needed, showing how individualization becomes systematically reproduced across policy levels despite theoretical expectations that decentralization would enable diverse local responses.

Moreover, our analysis reveals a prevailing emphasis on early interventions that are underpinned by a market-driven logic that prioritizes accountability and performance metrics, often at the expense of structural change. While economic arguments can help highlight resource disparities, they risk reinforcing deficit-based approaches that stigmatize marginalized communities rather than addressing systemic inequalities. In fact, there is a growing body of evidence showing that neoliberal politics, particularly the commodification of ECEC, and its insistence on competition, calculation and choice actually increases inequality and decreases inclusion (Magnússon, 2023; Roberts-Holmes & Moss, 2021; Vandenbroeck et al., 2023). Future policy should take this into account and expand its analytic scope beyond individually focused intervention and be sensitive to broader socio-political structures that shape inequalities in education, such as housing segregation and school privatization. Additionally, pedagogical innovations, including aesthetic and community-based approaches linked to the paradigm of *The Commons*, offer promising pathways for inclusive education that foster belonging and collective engagement.

Which subject positions do these interpretations create and allow for children? Of the five subject positions we identified, only the co-producer perspective fully acknowledges children as active participants. The other positions primarily frame children as passive recipients of knowledge, shaped by predetermined developmental, economic, or linguistic paradigms. This restrictive framing reinforces a narrow, interventionist approach to inclusion, where children are positioned as needing to assimilate rather than contribute. Even the co-producer perspective, while promising, risks being appropriated within governance models that emphasize adaptability and self-regulation rather than genuine participation (Fendler, 2001; Rose, 1999; Rose & Abi-Rached, 2013). This raises broader concerns about how educational policy defines children's roles in society: whether as

subjects of intervention or as active co-constructors of culture and knowledge (Korsgaard, 2018; Pechtelidis & Kioupkiolis, 2020). To challenge these constraints, we argue for a pedagogical shift that moves beyond transmission-based models and recognizes children as *commoners* engaged in *commoning* practices and the creation of new *common goods* (culture, knowledge, and values) in education and society (Pechtelidis & Kioupkiolis, 2020).

Which dominant beliefs and ideas about children's social, environmental and political activity, and their entitlement to participate in public life, do the discourses include? Our analysis revealed a significant policy shift in which inequalities and inclusion are increasingly framed through the lens of Swedish language acquisition, reinforcing a compensatory and reproductive logic. By prioritizing linguistic competence as the primary condition for inclusion, these policies overlook pedagogical insights into multimodal, play-based, and aesthetic learning. Without recognition of these diverse modes of communication, interventions may not only fail to achieve their intended goals but could also reinforce exclusion. Moving forward, it is important to develop policies that integrate broader pedagogical and transdisciplinary insights that highlight the developmental contributions of multimodal and aesthetic perspectives.

In developing policies and guidance related to early childhood language development, it is therefore critical to draw on relevant pedagogical knowledge concerning multimodality, play, aesthetics and exploration, otherwise attempts at inclusion will fall short, or even have a counter-productive effect. There is a real threat that hardening divisions along identitarian and geographical lines currently drawn up in the public debate in Sweden and elsewhere in Europe will unwittingly come to influence educational policies and legislations, and that sound scientific knowledge concerning pedagogical questions will become obscured. This could possibly lead to yet more neglect and even deliberate resistance to efforts aimed at reversing inequalities and promoting active inclusion in education and society.

While we critique both the focus on language and the rush toward “readiness for school”, which often prioritizes direct language instruction over exploratory and play oriented approaches, we recognize that language acquisition need not conflict with such approaches. Indeed, project-based work as well as play and aesthetically oriented collaborative activities can support language development while preserving the open, exploratory nature of preschool education. At the same time, we acknowledge that the notion of playful and aesthetic exploration in early childhood education is historically situated in the context of a post-industrial, largely middle-class society like Sweden. However, we argue that the principles behind this approach—encouraging creativity, curiosity, and critical thinking—can be adapted to diverse cultural and economic contexts.

Finally, what all discourses in the analyzed documents have in common is a prospective vs. a here-and-now view of childhood (Kristjánsson, 2006). Children are considered as not yet full-fledged citizens, and they are not entitled to fully participate in public life. Addressing inequalities through inclusive education is thus framed in terms of *preparing* children to become citizens who participate in public life *in the future* and *after their education*. This future-oriented framing is reinforced by the language-focused inclusion discourse we identified, which, as Papakosma (2024) shows reflects “a shift from a resource-orientated view of multilingualism towards a competence-orientated prioritization of proficiency in languages, especially Swedish” (p. 313) linked to “future social

and economic integration” (p. 314) rather than valuing children’s current multilingual capabilities and their right to participate fully in preschool life here and now.

Despite the weaknesses that the above images present, opportunities remain for educators, researchers and policymakers to collaborate in advancing ideas of the task of education when addressing inequality and inclusion that comprise both a compensatory *and* a complementary function. Further, there are always possibilities to insist upon images of the child as co-producer of culture, knowledge, and values, including through engaging in more innovative and aesthetic methodologies within the paradigm of *The Commons*. There are also examples in the analyzed documents of genuine ambitions to acknowledge, encourage and actively work for the reversal of inequalities in early childhood education. The fact that some of these formulations exist in official legislations and policies is an important strength. Furthermore, the fact that access to education is highly subsidized or free of charge and that the youngest children are not (yet) formally and individually assessed and graded in the Swedish ECEC system, presents valuable opportunities for exploration and development of equal and inclusive education, where the new generation may—with their social, environmental and political activities—participate more fully in public life here and now. As noted, this demands new policies and transdisciplinary efforts to resolve larger structural issues, as well as more innovative methodologies and a revised image of children’s active participation in public life, where they can be recognized as *commoners*, engaged in *commoning* practices, contributing both to educational and societal *common goods* (Pechtelidis & Kioupkiolis, 2020).

Appendices

Documents and resources analysed

- Education Act (2010:800) https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/skollag-2010800_sfs-2010-800
- The Discrimination Act (2008:567) https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/diskrimineringslag-2008567_sfs-2008-567
- Governmental Investigation on equality and social inclusion in primary and secondary school *A more equal school – Decreased segregation and increased distribution of resources* (SOU 2020:28) <https://www.regeringen.se/rattsliga-dokument/statens-offentliga-utredningar/2020/04/sou-202028/>
- Swedish Preschool Curriculum (National Agency of Education, 2018) <https://www.skolverket.se/getFile?file=4001>
- Governmental Investigation recommending compulsory preschool for certain children *More children in preschool – For better language acquisition in Swedish* (SOU 2020:67) <https://www.regeringen.se/rattsliga-dokument/statens-offentliga-utredningar/2020/11/sou-202067/>
- Preschool Board’s Action Plan (2021). [Title and full bibliographic details withheld to protect the anonymity of the research site.]

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Author contributions

The authors contributed equally to the production of this manuscript.

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Data availability

The data analysed in this study consist of publicly available policy documents. A comprehensive list of these documents, including their titles and direct URLs for access, is provided in manuscript appendix.

Declarations

Competing interests

The authors have no financial and non-financial competing interests.

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